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A critical study of a program designed for transforming India into a digitally empowered and knowledgeable economy

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Abstract

Digital India is not only a programme but it is a Revolutionary step to transform mostly our society into digital empowered society as well as a knowledgeable society. This Revolutionary step was taken by our honorable P.M. Mr Narendra Modi to provide all services specially government services to each and every citizen and up to the last Citizen of the nation electronically very fast and quickly. The main aim of this programme is to bring India towards a new technological world by providing Central Technology for all programme and government services under one roof. The main motto behind this concept to bring transparency in government schemes. Digital India is one of the Revolutionary steps taken by the government to transform and motivate society into digital empowerment society.

This paper helps to know various challenges that create obstacles in the successful implementation of this programme and also suggests some remedial actions to remove the obstacles and see whether it is beneficial to all the citizens or only for few because India is very vast country and the percentage of Technical and computerized knowledge person are very low so it maybe this program are still very far from most of the citizen of the society.

Key words:

Digital India Key areas, Scope , Pillars, Challenges and Suggetions.

Introduction:-Digital India is an umbrella programme which totally depends on the technology and has only a vision that converts India into a digitally empowered society and knowledgeable economy. Digital India is a flagship programme, its main aim to develop infrastructure system, Before digital India programme there were some programmes and projects were adopted by the government but due to the interactive system and in the presence of isolation it becomes fail, so it was very urgent need of comprehensive planning and its implementation for this government wanted to create new infrastructure. On the recommendation of the govt there was a participative, transparent and responsive programmes launched name was given Digital India Programme. What Is Digital India Programme ? The answer of this Question is , Digital India is an umbrella programme which is totally depend on the technology which has only a vision that converting India into a digital empowered society and knowledgeable economy. To achieve this objective an Ecosystem was established,with the help of Department of Electronics and Information Technology connecting all the Ministries and Govt. Departments for providing services under one roof with the help of an information system. A programme to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. This is a follow-up to the key decisions taken on the design of the programme during the meeting of the Prime Minister on Digital India Programme on August 7, 2014, and to sensitize all ministries to this vast programme touching every corner of the government. This programme has been envisaged by Department of Electronics and Information Technology (DeitY). The vision of Digital India aims to transform the country into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. The programme will be implemented in phases from the current year till 20The Digital India is transformational in nature and would ensure that Government services are available to citizens electronically. It would also bring in public accountability through mandated delivery of government services electronically, a Unique ID, and e-Pramaan based on authentic and standard-based interoperable and integrated government applications and data basis.

The Key areas of Digital India:

I Infrastructure as Utility to Every Citizen:

- (i) High speed internet as a core utility shall be made available in all Gram Panchayats. Cradle to grave digital identity - unique, lifelong, online and authenticable.**
- (ii) Mobile phone and Bank account would enable participation in digital and financial space at individual level.**
- (iii) Easy access to a Common Service Centre within their locality.**
- (iv) Shareable private space on a public Cloud.**
- (v) Safe and secure Cyber-space in the country.**

II Governance and Services on Demand:

- (i) Seamlessly integrated across departments or jurisdictions to provide easy and a single window access to all persons.**
- (ii) Government services available in real time from online and mobile platforms.**

- (iii) All citizen entitlements to be available on the Cloud to ensure easy access.
- (iv) Government services digitally transformed for improving Ease of Doing Business.
- (v) Making financial transactions above a threshold, electronic and cashless.
- (vi) Leveraging GIS for decision support systems and development.

III Digital Empowerment of Citizens:

- (i) Universal digital literacy.
- (ii) All digital resources universally accessible.
- (iii) All Government documents/ certificates to be available on the Cloud.
- (iv) Availability of digital resources / services in Indian languages.
- (v) Collaborative digital platforms for participative governance.
- (vi) Portability of all entitlements for individuals through the Cloud.

Scope of Digital India:

The overall scope of this programme is:

- (i) To prepare India for a knowledge future.
- (ii) On being transformative that is to realize IT (Indian Talent) + IT (Information Technology) = IT (India Tomorrow)
- (iii) Making technology central to enabling change.
- (iv) On being an Umbrella Programme – covering many departments.

□□□□□□□□□□ The programme weaves together a large number of ideas and thoughts into a single, comprehensive vision, so that each of them is seen as part of a larger goal. Each individual element stands on its own, but is also part of the larger picture.

□□□□□□□□□□ The weaving together makes the Mission transformative in totality.

- (v) The Digital India Programme will pull together many existing schemes which would be restructured and re-focused and implemented in a synchronized manner. The common branding of the programmes as Digital India, highlights their transformative impact.

Digital India aims to provide the much needed thrust to the nine pillars of growth areas, namely

1. Broadband Highways,
2. Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity,
3. Public Internet Access Programme,

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4. **e-Governance: Reforming Government through Technology,**
 5. **e-Kranti - Electronic Delivery of Services,**
 6. **Information for All,**
 7. **Electronics Manufacturing,**
 8. **IT for Jobs**
 9. **Early Harvest Programmes.**

DIGITAL INDIA: CHALLENGES

1. **Digital illiteracy:** Digital illiteracy is prevalent in most of the towns and villages in India. Cities have adopted digitalization but are limited to a certain extent. Full-fledged digitalization is cashless transactions on a daily basis and, the use of internet services to get government certificates. This requires administration changes, Taxation changes, and changes in public mentality. So it's a teamwork that includes citizen's responsibility and support to the new system.
2. **Connectivity to remote areas.** The problem of connectivity is a complex issue because every state has different laws pertaining to its execution. Also, it is challenging for the central authorities to make a database where such a huge information can be stored.
3. **Compatibility with center state databases:** Every state has different internet protocols because every state is diversified. Diversified not only in the sense of religion but also in language. Hence software compatibility with the center is a crucial issue. Information shall be saved carefully.
4. **Inter-Departmental Co ordination:** Within the government, various departments should be integrated. Integration has technical as well as corporate issue. Corporate in the sense self ego of the officers and staff of our government services are hurdle in the change. Also, the middle man policy will be eliminated completely because of digital India, hence there will be imminent resistance from the working staff.
5. **Cyber Crime:** There is cyber threat all over the globe and digital India will not be any exception. Hence we need a strong anti cyber crime team which maintains the database and protects it round the clock.
6. **Changing the mindset:** This point will come into picture when you have allocated the required resources and material but when it comes to implementing them, most of them will be hesitant to change. People are accustomed with years of same of practice that they are not ready to change.
7. **Finance:** Though there are resources with India but there is a huge capital cost which is to be invested and the fruits of the investment will be received after few year.

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8. Exchange of information: The information stored should also be used by other government offices. For example police, surveillance and other security issues can be easily resolved with digital India but its coordination is a mammoth task. It is not only a technological question but also deals with the question of privacy
 9. Net neutrality: The issue is still on the table and we are blindly following the digital India. Net neutrality is must and we should make sure that digital India without net neutrality would be a great blow to entrepreneurs and citizens of India.

Recommendations:

Digital India campaign can't be successful on its own. Policy changes are needed to make digital India a reality. Few of the suggestions are –

1. Digital literacy is the first step in empowering citizens. People should know how to secure their online data.
2. To make this programme successful, a massive awareness programme has to be conducted. There is a pressing need to educate and inform the citizens, especially in rural and remote areas, about the benefits of internet services to increase the growth of internet usage.
3. The digital divide needs to be addressed.
4. Manufacturing content is not the government's strength. This mission needs content and service partnerships with telecom companies and other firms.
5. PPP models must be explored for the sustainable development of digital infrastructure.
6. The private sector should be encouraged for the development of last-mile infrastructure in rural and remote areas. To encourage the private sector, there must be favorable taxation policies, and quicker clearance of projects.
7. The success of the digital India project depends upon maximum connectivity with minimum cyber security risks. For this, we need a strong anti-cybercrime team that maintains the database and protects it around the clock.
8. To improve skills in cyber security, we need to introduce cyber security courses at the graduate level and encourage international certification bodies to introduce various skill-based cyber security courses.
9. There is a need for effective participation of various departments and demanding commitment and efforts. Various policies in different areas should support this goal.
10. For successful implementation, there must be amendments in various legislations that have for long hindered the growth of technology in India.

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